

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

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ISSIQXONALARDAGI INSON-O'SIMLIKLAR-ATROF MUXIT TEXNOLOGIYASI TIZIMIDA ISHCHI AYOL-QIZLAR ISHTROKI, ISSIQLIKNING NAZARIY ASPEKTLARI.

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Kalit so'zlar: issiqxona, inson, ayol-qizlar, kasbiy kasallik, iqlim, ekologik muammo, xavfsizlik, texnik xizmat ko'rsatish.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada, hududlar aholisini sabzavot mahsulotlari bilan (mavsumiy yoki yil davomida) ta'minlash muammosi, ularning geografik joylashuvi va iqlimini hisobga olgan holda, mamlakatning aksariyat hududlari sharoitida qo'riqlanadigan yerlarning eng keng tarqalgan inshootlari bo'lgan issiqxonalardan foydalanish orqali hal qilinadi. Ushbu tuzilmalar yetarlicha mashhurlikka erishdi va hozirgacha odamlarni kuz-qish-bahor davrida boyitilgan sabzavot mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlashning yagona ishonchli manbai hisoblanadi. Issiqxona tizimida faoliyat olib borayotgan ayollar va qizlar roli, faoliyat jarayonida ortirilgan ayollar kasbiy kasalliklariga qarshi chora-tadbirlar, qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtirishda noto'g'ri o'ylangan qayta qurish islohotlaridan so'ng agrosanoat ishlab chiqarishining tiklanishi munosabati bilan himoyalangan tuproq ishlab chiqarishga ehtiyoj ortishi haqidagi ma'lumotlar yoritildi.

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF HEAT, PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN AND GIRLS WORKING IN GREENHOUSES IN THE TECHNOLOGY SYSTEM HUMAN-PLANTS- ENVIRONMENT.

Key words: greenhouse, human, woman-girls, occupational disease, climate, environmental problem, safety, maintenance.

Abstract. In this article, the problem of providing the population of the regions with vegetable products (seasonally or year-round) in the conditions of most regions of the country, given their geographical location and climate are decided by the use of greenhouses - the most common structures of protected ground. These structures have gained sufficient popularity and are so far the only reliable source of providing people with fortified vegetable products in the autumn-winter-spring period. Information was covered about the role of women and girls operating in the greenhouse system, measures against female occupational diseases increased in the process of activity, the increased need for protected soil production in connection with the restoration of agro-industrial production after incorrectly thought-out reconstruction reforms in the cultivation of agricultural products.

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ТЕПЛООБРАБОТКИ, УЧАСТИЕ ЖЕНЩИН И ДЕВУШЕК РАБОТАЮЩИХ В ТЕПЛИЦАХ В ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ ЧЕЛОВЕК-РАСТЕНИЯ - ОКРУЖАЮЩАЯ СРЕДА.

Ключевые слова: теплица, человек, женщины, профессиональные заболевания, экологические проблемы, климат

Аннотация: Проблему обеспечения населения регионов овощной продукцией (сезонно или круглогодично) в условиях большинства регионов страны с учетом их географического положения и климата решает использование теплиц-наиболее распространенных сооружений защищенного грунта. Эти сооружения приобрели достаточную популярность и являются пока единственным надежным источником обеспечения населения витаминизированной растительной продукцией в осенне-зимне-весенний период. Освещена роль женщин и девушек, работающих в тепличной системе, меры по борьбе с женскими профессиональными заболеваниями, приобретенными в процессе деятельности, повышенная потребность в защищенном почвенном производстве в связи с восстановлением агропромышленного производства после непродуманных реструктуризационных реформ в сельском хозяйстве.

Consequently, greenhouse complexes will develop in the near and long term. This is especially important in areas close to large cities. Hopes for import substitution are not always adequate for domestic production; in addition, the feasibility of import substitution of vegetable products, taking into account a set of economic and qualitative indicators in terms of nutritional value, in some cases it is not only expedient, but also effective. Therefore, in the suburban agricultural zones

of almost all regions of the country, cultivation facilities have become widespread (and continue to expand). Protected ground - greenhouses and greenhouse complexes. The economic feasibility of such decisions is beyond doubt, as well as the social feasibility in terms of the supply of vegetables. At the same time, they need to be assessed and, as the results of studies [11.B.3] show, improve the working conditions of the personnel working in them (as a rule, the vast majority are women), since the production of fruit and vegetable products in cultivation facilities is accompanied by injuries and morbidity of workers. However, the theoretical provisions of the "greenhouse-man-plants-technologies-technology-environment" (T-Ch-P-Te-Tx-Sr) system have not been developed to date.

The purpose of the study is the theoretical substantiation of the system "Greenhouses-man-plants-technologies-equipment-environment" in terms of labor protection parameters and analysis of their relationship and mutual influence on the operators working there.

Materials, methods and objects of research. As research materials, the results of studying and analyzing working conditions, the level and causes of injuries and production-related diseases of workers in cultivation facilities in the production of vegetable products (especially in hazardous and highly hazardous types of work, including maintenance, repair and replacement of glass ceilings of inclined surfaces of greenhouse roofs) are considered. The research methods were based on the results of field surveys of labor protection parameters at the objects under consideration, taking into account the features of work, production technologies, the equipment used and the environmental conditions characteristic of the object. The provisions of the logical analysis of the system under consideration in terms of labor protection parameters are used. The object of research was greenhouses and greenhouse complexes, the production technologies used in them, their maintenance and repair, greenhouse workers, the equipment used and the available environment, characteristic of the object.

Research results. Concerning this problem, we note that the labor activity of workers there is carried out in the system C "greenhouse T-man H - plant P - technology Technique Tx-environment Sr" (T-Ch-P-Te-TX-SR). An analysis of the components of this system C gives grounds to assert that each of them is intended to solve certain tasks of Zp provided for by the ultimate goal of C. These tasks, subject to the general expediency, are solved by specific ways of PS, which are distinguished by a large variety of Pm in terms of the implementation of the CPP, the technologies for implementing the TR, the agrobiological AB used for this, energy E resources and life support systems. Recall that the tasks implemented at different stages of production are subordinated to a common goal - obtaining products P. O operators have to adapt to the production conditions of the UE in order to comply with the requirements of the TN of the regulatory framework [14.B.8] in terms of conditions, safety and harmlessness of the work of the UB. Thus, there is a complex greenhouse-technological human-machine system with complex relationships, interdependencies and mutual influence. In the general case, the description of the above in an analytical form can be represented by the following dependencies:

components of system C to achieve goal C:

$$C = f_1(T - \Psi - P - Te - TX - CP) SR$$

The analysis of the given dependencies shows that they are decisive in the system (T-Ch-R-Te-TX-SR) in the intended purpose of the problem. Their inner content production, economic and labor protection parameters is the basis for a successful solution of the problem, taking into account the relationships and their mutual influence on each other and the final results (objective function). For analysis, it is expedient to present the outlined main provisions of the problem graphically,[4.B.5] which is shown in fig.1

Figure. 1. Schematic diagram of functioning and interrelations in the system (T-Ch-R-T e-T X-S R); the decoding of the parameters is given above in the text

Let us give a brief description of the components of the last equality. The OT parameter refers to the greenhouse (object) as a whole as a socialized object for the production of vegetable products (cucumber, tomatoes, lettuce, dill, green onions, seedlings, radishes, parsley, celery, mushrooms, etc.) [17.B.8]. The named parameter is mainly characterized by the purpose for growing vegetable crops O TC, which determines its parameters O TP, internal equipment O TV, technologies O TE, microclimate O TM, etc. O T.D. sanitary standards are established by girls and women under the age of 18 in order to ensure optimal working conditions in the performance of work related to lifting and transporting heavy loads, to prevent violations of reproductive function and state of Health. It is mandatory to comply with these sanitary standards and rules by all enterprises, organizations and associations, as well as individual individuals, regardless of the form of ownership.

1. It is allowed to carry and transport goods to girls under 18 years of age if they do not exceed the norms listed below and are associated with the work they perform constantly and consist of a third of the working time.

2. Girls under the age of 18 are not allowed to engage in activities that carry loads weighing only 4.1 kg.

3. For girls under 18 years old, the mass of manual lifting and transportation of cargo should not exceed 7 kg.

Girls under 4.18 years of age are not allowed to transport goods in one-wheeled stretchers and in a two-wheeled stroller.

5. When transporting heavy goods in three-and four-wheeled trolleys, the limit weight of the cargo should not exceed 52 kg, while transportation on a flat surface is allowed with a limit lifting indicator of 0.01.

6. When heavy loads are transported in carriages, the limit weight of the load should not exceed 224 kg, in which it is allowed to move only on the rails, with a lifting indicator not exceeding 0.01.

7. For girls 14-15 years old, manual lifting and transportation of goods is allowed in exceptional cases, in which all regulatory loads recorded in 3 points are reduced by 2 times.

8. For girls 14-15 years old, cargo is not allowed to be transported in strollers, mattresses and carriages [5.B.6].

Mirziyayev SH. M. In his speech at a meeting dedicated to the analysis of reforms, "let the reforms in the field of Medicine serve the satisfaction of the population from life, the development of our country. Special attention has been paid to issues related to" further improvement of the health system, improving the quality and efficiency of medical services, strengthening the health of the population, providing quality medicines " and Development [7.B.3]. More than half of the world's population is employed, so the socio-economic development of each country depends on the health, safety, working capacity and well-being of workers. Healthy workers are productive workers. Dismissal due to work-related illness and incapacity for work disrupts the activities of enterprises and undermines their reputation, increasing costs such as attracting and training new employees to social and health care costs. Safety and health during operation also contribute positively to the profitability and national economy of the enterprise by increasing efficiency [8.B.96.].

At the initiative of, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan SH.M.Mirziyoyev information was provided by the Fergana Region Department of innovative development on greenhouses from 3 acres, which are planned to be built on the farm of each family included in the "iron and women's notebook".

Earlier, 30 cases of apartments and apartments provided by the municipality of Sixtiariq district were studied at the address. From the list of 30 households, 15 families with the most serious condition were selected. These apartments are included in the “iron and women's notebook” for various reasons: lost a family breadwinner, a family member became seriously ill and became disabled, and other reasons. It was determined that the greenhouses will be finished and put into operation by the date of August 31 of this year. When performing all, without exception, technological processes in the greenhouse sector, regulatory and legal working conditions for workers must be ensured. As practice and individual studies show, people working there (usually women) are exposed to elevated temperatures and humidity for a long time (about 80-88% of the shift). In addition, there are drafts leading to colds, as well as injuries associated with falls from a height (when harvesting) and on a flat surface. In case of violation of labor protection measures during dusting and spraying plants with various solutions, the air in greenhouses contains vapors of spraying liquids and dusting preparations, which does not contribute to air purity. With insufficient ventilation and ventilation of the internal volume of greenhouses, normalized air purity is not guaranteed even a few days after the measures taken. A number of internal equipment of greenhouses, carts used for harvesting and transporting crops, glass roofs, etc. do not meet elementary safety requirements, which creates risks of injury, which are often realized.

Conclusion. The stated situation, which lasts for decades, cannot be considered normal and requires a theoretical analysis of the system under consideration. The above theoretical aspects make it possible to determine the factors of each of the components of the system in their relationship and mutual influence on the safety and health of work. The specification of these factors in the system under consideration allows us to determine preventive measures. In the direction of the strategy and tactics of dynamic reduction and elimination of injuries and industrially caused diseases in the production of vegetable products in

the cultivation facilities of protected ground. In this area of prevention, the most important is a set of labor protection measures, the priority of which in terms of production technologies, methods and means of their implementation are engineering and technical, sanitary and hygienic, socio-economic, ergonomic and organizational and technical. In this direction, the decisive word belongs to labor protection science and best practices for using its results.

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